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- *Modern studies in fiction literature translation*
- *Current approaches to terminology translation and interpreting*
- *Contemporary research in mass-media translation and interpretation*

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CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH IN MASS-MEDIA TRANSLATION AND INTERPRETATION

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MODERN STUDIES IN FICTION LITERATURE TRANSLATION

PRAGMALINGUISTIC ANALYSIS AS MODERN STUDY IN FICTION LITERARY TRANSLATION

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The research is devoted to a new approach to the fiction literature translation study based on the analysis of the speech behavior of Vladimir Nabokov and the translators of his novel “Lolita”. The methodological basis of the study is a pragmalinguistic experiment with elements of modified content analysis. The study was conducted within the framework of Implicit Pragmalinguistics. To analyze the original text and its translations, the implicit speech strategy “Participation / non-participation of communicants in a speech event” was chosen. The main conclusion: translators should minimize their interference so that addressees see the author's intention, and not the translator's individuality.

BILINGUALISM AND IDENTITY: THE PRACTICE OF SELF-TRANSLATION AMONG ROMANIAN AUTHORS

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This research explores the complex interplay between bilingualism, identity and literary creation, focusing on the practice of self-translation among Romanian and Moldovan authors. It delves into the historical roots of linguistic diversity in the region, examines prominent literary figures who navigated multiple languages, and analyzes the unique challenges and opportunities presented by self-translation as a creative act. At first glance, self-translation may appear to be an ideal solution to many of the challenges posed by literary translation. However, a closer examination reveals that self-translation is a far more complex and demanding process than it initially seems. It requires not only a deep mastery of both languages but also the ability to recreate literary style, tone and cultural context without compromising artistic integrity. Due to these high demands and the pressure to meet rigorous literary standards in more than one language, self-translation remains a rare and exceptional practice in the literary world.

DOCTORAL RESEARCH ON TRANSLATED FICTION IN 21ST-CENTURY ROMANIA: A METACRITICAL APPROACH

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By looking at 46 PhD dissertations defended in Romanian universities in the 21st century, I aim to offer a glimpse of doctoral research on fiction in translation and the ways in which it reflects the current trends in translation (theory) in general. To this end, I adopt a metacritical approach (based on various Translation Studies taxonomies) which highlights regularities and trends in doctoral research in the field of Translation Studies.

**FEMININE POWER ‘LOST’ AND FEMININE POWER ‘REGAINED’:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TALBOT DONALDSON’S (1966),
SEAMUS HEANEY’S (1999) AND MARIA DAHVANA HEADLEY’S (2018)
TRANSLATIONS OF BEOWULF**

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Translations of “Beowulf” often obscure the role of women in Anglo-Saxon society: formal equivalence translators, such as Talbot Donaldson (1966), replicate the text literally, but lack clarity, while dynamic equivalence translators, such as Seamus Heaney (1999), prioritize modern readability over accuracy. Both approaches diminish female authority and often reduce women to mead-bearers and mourners. Maria Dahvana Headley (2018), in her turn, breaks tradition with her subversive transcreation of “Beowulf” in the novel “The Mere Wife”, which centers on female characters. This paper compares translations of “Beowulf” by Donaldson, Heaney, and Headley, so as to reclaim the female power present in the original Old English epic but lost in subsequent patriarchal renditions.

CULTURAL TRANSFER THROUGH THE TRANSLATIONS OF TWO BALKAN WRITERS' NOVELS WRITTEN IN ENGLISH

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This paper focuses on the works of two Balkan writers, Elif Shafak and Kapka Kasabova, and their translation into Romanian. The two authors, of Turkish and Bulgarian origin, respectively, write their novels in English. Following the Cultural Transfer Approach as the main method of investigation, the current research dwells on the tripartite process of cultural mediation through translation.

**THE METAMORPHOSIS OF MEDICAL LATIN:
A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF TERMINOLOGICAL CHALLENGES
IN ENGLISH TRANSLATION**

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The study examines the challenges of translating medical Latin terminology into modern English, focusing on semantic shifts that create "false friends" between the languages. Through analysis of terms like "remedium," "therapia," and phrases such as "crisis morbi", the research reveals how seemingly straightforward translations can lead to functional misinterpretations in medical discourse. The paper argues that effective translation requires understanding not only etymological connections but also the current functional use of terminology in contemporary medical contexts. Analysis of historical medical texts and contemporary academic materials demonstrates that appropriate translation is predicated on functional equivalence rather than literal interpretation for the preservation of intended medical significance across linguistic boundaries.

EMPOWERING ENGLISH LEARNERS THROUGH TRANSLATING DIVERSE YOUNG ADULT FICTION VOICES

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The study aims to promote English language learning through the translation of diverse young adult (YA) fiction texts, thereby encouraging linguistic and cultural competence. Using a qualitative methodology, 30 intermediate English learners translated extracts from multicultural YA novels (e.g. *The Hate U Give*). Data were collected through translation tasks and reflective surveys and analyzed using a thematic coding methodology. The results show that vocabulary, cultural awareness and engagement were improved. Integrating short translation activities into YA literature helps to create an inclusive and interactive learning environment, in line with the principles of communicative language teaching. Interventions with digital translation tools can enhance accessibility and merit further investigation.

**LANGUAGE OF VIOLENCE IN TRANSLATION:
EXPLORING IDENTITY IN LILIANA COROBCA'S *KINDERLAND***

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Helmuth Popitz (1992) defines violence as an act of power that results in the intended bodily harm of others, no matter whether the purpose of this act is contained in itself, or used as a threat, it is intended to establish a permanent submission. Liliana Corobca's "*Kinderland*" depicts the hardships of children left behind in rural Moldova, exposing subtle forms of violence: emotional, structural, and neglect. This study examines the linguistic devices used to represent these forms of violence in the novel and analyses the translation procedures based on Peter Newmark's typology, employed to render them from a contrastive Romanian–English perspective.

**“CHOOSE WITH CARE”: AN ANALYSIS OF THE TRANSLATION
OF RACIST SLANG AND NON-SLANG TERMS SUCH AS “BLACK”,
“DARKIE”, “NIGGER”, AND “NEGRO” INTO TURKISH
IN ANDREA LEVY’S “SMALL ISLAND”**

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This paper analyzes the translation of racist slang and non-slang terms, including “Black,” “Darkie,” “Nigger,” and “Negro” into Turkish in Andrea Levy’s novel *Small Island* (2004) to show the complexities of translating the concepts that do not have Turkish equivalents and the significance of the translator’s endeavour to preserve the emotional, historical and cultural value of the original text. In *Small Island*, Andrea Levy (1956-2019) depicts the interconnected lives of four characters - two Jamaicans, Hortense and Gilbert, and two Britons, Queenie and Bernard - grappling with themes of race, identity, and post-World War II immigration in England. For the racist comments in the novel, the words “Black,” “Darkie,” “Nigger,” and “Negro” are used, each carrying a distinct degree of offensiveness. However, these racist phrases, such as “Darkie,” “Nigger,” and “Negro,” which have a unique racial history in English, lack obvious Turkish equivalents because for the word “Black,” only two words, “siyahi” and “zenci,” which do not have offensive meanings compared to English, are used. The aim of this paper is, thus, to present how the translator, who

does not pay attention to their usage in both languages, employs them arbitrarily throughout the translation process, regardless of the context. This approach fails to demonstrate the intended level of offensiveness in the original text and fails to accurately convey the same depth of meaning.

DIRECT AND INDIRECT TRANSLATION STRATEGIES IN “DICK WHITTINGTON AND HIS CAT”

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In the research, I analyze the direct and indirect translation strategies used in rendering phraseological units from the English folk tale “Dick Whittington and his cat” into Romanian. The present analysis is grounded in the translation procedures formulated by Jean-Paul Vinay and Jean Darbelnet in their work “*Stylistique comparée du français et de l’anglais*” / “Comparative Stylistics of French and English” (1958/1995). These procedures are commonly grouped into direct strategies and indirect strategies. The conclusions will verify whether indirect strategies are prevalent in the English–Romanian translation due to the typological distance between English (a Germanic language) and Romanian (a Romance language).

**L'INTERFÉRENCE DE L'ARABE MAROCAIN SUR LE FRANÇAIS
AU COLLÈGE : CAS DE L'ORAL AU MAROC /**

**THE INTERFERENCE OF MOROCCAN ARABIC ON FRENCH
IN MIDDLE SCHOOL: A CASE STUDY OF SPOKEN LANGUAGE IN MOROCCO**

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In multilingual education systems, teaching French as a foreign language (FLE) presents complex challenges, particularly in the area of oral production. In Morocco, where several languages coexist (dialectal Arabic, Amazigh, Classical Arabic, and French), students often encounter specific difficulties when expressing themselves orally in French. These difficulties are not solely due to limited vocabulary or grammatical knowledge; rather, they are deeply rooted in the linguistic and cognitive phenomenon of interference.

Linguistic interference occurs when learners unconsciously transfer elements from their mother tongue, such as vocabulary, phonetics, or syntax, into the foreign language they are learning. In the case of Moroccan middle school students, this transfer often manifests through pronunciation errors, gender confusion, lexical calques, and grammatical constructions influenced by dialectal Arabic or Tamazight.

Oral proficiency is a central objective in FLE instruction, particularly at the middle school level, where students must be prepared to interact, debate, express themselves clearly, and understand others in a language that is not their own. In this context, it becomes essential to systematically study the impact of linguistic interference on students' oral production, both to understand its mechanisms and causes, and to develop effective teaching strategies to mitigate its effects.

Our communication aligns with this objective. It aims to explore the most frequent types of linguistic interference among 3rd-year middle school students, to analyze the contributing factors, and to examine their influence on oral performance.

**TRADUIRE LA LITTÉRATURE D'ENFANCE ET DE JEUNESSE.
LES CLASSIQUES FRANÇAIS TRADUITS VERS LE ROUMAIN /**

**TRANSLATING CHILDREN'S LITERATURE.
THE FRENCH CLASSICS IN ROMANIAN TRANSLATION**

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Children's Literature is one of the most dynamic and interesting corpus of analysis in Translation Studies. Our research is a contribution to the study of its place in the history of literary translation, with examples from French classics translated into Romanian. The History of Translation into Romanian, a monumental project that is still in progress, will be often cited as a rich resource of data for the 20th century, which is particularly interesting for our study as it is the period of retranslations, where the multimodal dimension of translated texts is enhanced. Issues such as translator's visibility and editorial strategies of modernizing older texts will be included in the study.

SAINT JÉRÔME, TRADUCTOLOGUE AVANT LA LETTRE /

SAINT JEROME, A TRANSLATION THEORIST BEFORE THE TERM EXISTED

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Saint Jerome, considered the patron saint of translators, was a prominent scholar who lived at the end of IVth - beginning of the Vth centuries. He is the author of a monumental work composed of theological writings, translations, reflections upon translation, as well as letters. He is mainly known for his Latin translation of the Bible, a version which remains in use in the Western Christianity. Recognizing such a prolific activity may be important for translators and translation studies specialists. In this presentation we will also be giving a few precious examples of Jerome’s reflections upon translation extracted from his letters, as well as from the prefaces of his works.

**REALIEN ALS KULTURTRÄGER: SADOVEANUS "HANU ANCUȚEI"
IN DEUTSCHER ÜBERSETZUNG /**

**REALIA AS CULTURAL BEARERS: SADOVEANU'S "HANU ANCUȚEI"
IN GERMAN TRANSLATION**

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The research explores the translation of *realia* – culturally specific elements unique to one language that often lack direct equivalents in another. Drawing on various theoretical frameworks, the paper defines *realia* as cultural signifiers whose accurate translation poses significant challenges. Particular attention is given to the complexities of conveying cultural concepts through a case study of Mihail Sadoveanu’s *Hanu AncuȚei* and its German translation. The analysis investigates the extent to which the German version preserves, alters, or omits culturally defining features of the original, as well as the translation strategies employed in the process. By focusing on onomastics, socio-historical terminology, and material cultural references, the study demonstrates that Sadoveanu’s portrayal of Moldavian life poses not only linguistic but also interpretive challenges for translators. Employing a corpus-based comparative approach, the study examines the Romanian original and its German translation to underscore the importance of accurately rendering *realia* in maintaining the authenticity and comprehensibility of the target text, thereby necessitating the use of varied and nuanced translation strategies.

**DER ÜBERSETZER ALS MITAUTOR? KREATIVE EINGRIFFE
IN VASILE ALECSANDRIS “PASTELLE” IM DEUTSCHEN /**

**THE TRANSLATOR AS CO-AUTHOR? CREATIVE INTERVENTIONS
IN VASILE ALECSANDRI'S “PASTELS” IN GERMAN**

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This research deals with the role of the translator as a co-author in the German translations of Vasile Alecsandri's "Pastels," focusing on the versions rendered by Carmen Sylva. It argues that literary translation surpasses mere semantic transfer, involving creative interventions that reshape poetic structures, emotional nuances, and cultural connotations. The study highlights how the translator's stylistic modifications and expansions generate an independent aesthetic framework, enhancing metaphorical imagery and adapting linguistic rhythm to German cultural expectations. By analyzing these transformative strategies, the article demonstrates the translator's active participation as a literary co-creator, contributing significantly to the reception and reinterpretation of Alecsandri's poetry in a new linguistic and cultural context.

**PALIMPSESTOS CROMÁTICOS: UNA APROXIMACIÓN
AL TRASVASE DE LOS TÉRMINOS RELACIONADOS CON EL COLOR
EN LAS TRADUCCIONES AL ESPAÑOL Y AL RUMANO
DE “FAHRENHEIT 451” /**

**CHROMATIC PALIMPSESTS: AN APPROACH TO TRANSPOSING
COLOR TERMS VIA THE RENDITION OF FAHRENHEIT 451
INTO SPANISH AND ROMANIAN**

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This research aims to trace the translational strategies employed by the Spanish and Romanian translators of *Fahrenheit 451* in rendering terms and collocations related to color. The major focus is on assessment of the degree of poetic resemblance, adjustment or deviation to or from the connotative load of the text under scrutiny. In addition, our contribution is also aimed at mapping the cultural shifts – if any – underlying the chromatic change induced by translatorial “infidelities”.

**INVENTIO, DISPOSITIO Y ELOCUTIO
EN LA OBRA “LA STEAUA” DE MIHAI EMINESCU
Y SU TRADUCCIÓN EN ESPAÑOL DE VICENTE APARICIO /**

**INVENTIO, DISPOSITIO AND ELOCUTIO
IN MIHAI EMINESCU'S “LA STEAUA” AND ITS TRANSLATION
IN SPANISH BY VICENTE APARICIO**

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We propose a detailed investigation of Vicente Aparicio’s Spanish translation of Mihai Eminescu’s poem “La steaua”. Our analysis adopts a dual theoretical perspective: on the one hand, we examine the poem’s deep structure and organization through the rhetorical notions of invention and disposition; on the other hand, we also focus on its surface structure, namely elocution. This approach allows us to explore both the mechanisms of meaning construction and the stylistic aspect of the translated version. Additionally, we employ a comparative-contrastive perspective to highlight the specific challenges posed by the process of translation.

**DIFICULTADES DE TRADUCCIÓN
Y DE TRANSFERENCIA CULTURAL DEL RUMANO AL ESPAÑOL
EN LA OBRA “GRĂDINA DE STICLĂ” DE TATIANA ȚÎBULEAC /
DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATION
AND CULTURAL TRANSFER FROM ROMANIAN INTO SPANISH
IN THE NOVEL “GRĂDINA DE STICLĂ” BY TATIANA TIBULEAC**

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The research deals with the analysis of the main challenges involved in translating the novel *Gradina de sticla* by Tatiana Tibuleac, from Romanian into Spanish. One of the primary difficulties lies in the use of Moldovan dialects. Additionally, the novel is deeply shaped by the Soviet and post-Soviet context and the constant presence of bilingualism, with a mixture of languages, especially Russian and “Moldovan”. Translating this novel is not only a linguistic task, but also an exercise in cultural and emotional interpretation.

**DESEMNARE, SEMNIFICAȚIE, SENS – APLICAREA CONCEPTELOR
DIN TEORIA LUI EUGEN COȘERIU ÎN STUDIAREA MANIEREI
DE TRADUCERE A DOUĂ CRONOGRAFE DIN SECOLUL AL XVII-LEA:
„HRONOGRAF DEN ÎNCEPUTUL LUMII”, DE NICOLAE MILESCU
SPĂTARUL ȘI „NOVĂ ADUNARE DI ISTORII”,
DE MITROPOLITUL DOSOFTEI AL MOLDOVEI (I) /**

**DESIGNATION, SIGNIFICATION, MEANING – APPLYING
EUGEN COȘERIU’S THEORETICAL CONCEPTS TO THE STUDY
OF TRANSLATION METHODS IN TWO 17th-CENTURY CHRONOGRAPHS:
„HRONOGRAF DEN ÎNCEPUTUL LUMII” (*HRONOGRAF FROM THE BE-
GINNING OF THE WORLD*) BY NICOLAE MILESCU SPĂTARUL
AND „NOVĂ ADUNARE DI ISTORII” (*NEW COLLECTION OF HISTORIES*)
BY METROPOLITAN DOSOFTEI OF MOLDAVIA (PART I)**

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The old literary Romanian language was to a large extent the result of constant literal practice applied to translations, rendered in one of the old literary Romanian dialects. Among the texts that were translated in old times, a number of them did not observe this tendency and revealed a specific detachment from the original text. The transla-

tions of the chronographs, for instance, provided a good example as autonomous literary genres, both in the universal and the Romanian literature. One such example is *The Chronograph from the Beginning of the World* (ms. 3517 BAR) that was translated, according to our sources, by a Moldavian scholar, Nicolae Milescu Spătarul, between 1658-1661, using two old Greek chronographs, that of Mattheos Kigalas *Νεῖα σύνοψις διαφορῶν ἱστοριῶν ἀρχομένη ἀπό κτίσεως κόσμου...*, and certain paragraphs from Dorotheos of Monemvasia's *Βιβλίον ἱστορικὸν περιέχον ἐν συνόψει διαφόρους καὶ ἐξόχους ἱστορίας ...* as well as other texts. Three decades later, between 1686–1693, while in exile in Poland, Metropolitan Dosoftei of Moldavia, another remarkable figure of the old Romanian culture, translated Mattheos Kigalas' chronograph, using the unique original entitled *New Collection of Histories...* (ms. 3456 BAR). To approach the translation methods applied to both Romanian versions, we rely on the theoretical differences advanced by Eugen Coșeriu, based on three concepts: *designation*, *significance* and *sense*. A comparative approach starting from Matheos Kigalas' original Greek text reveals two different methods of microtext translation, that of Nicolae Milescu's more autonomous translation as compared to the original Greek text and that of Metropolitan Dosoftei's, whose tendency was toward designation, but more literally-prone than the former.

DISCURS POLIMORF ÎN CORESPONDENȚA LUI VASILE VASILACHE /
POLYMORPHOUS DISCOURSE IN THE CORRESPONDENCE
OF VASILE VASILACHE

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Our research deals with the specific aspects of epistolary discourse organization in the love correspondence of the writer Vasile Vasilache. These letters, composite constructions *par excellence* in which the dominant discourse is erotic, are addressed to the young Marianna Lomako and are characterized by a heterogeneous thematic structure and enunciative polyphony. The polymorphism of the discourse is a defining feature of these letters, which are shaped both by sentiment and a narrative impulse. Within the epistolary space, the speaker inserts details about his intimate emotions, confessions about his creative activities, meditations, essayistic sequences, mini-reviews of literary works, short stories, journal entries, paraphrases, and more - all of which reveal the writer's deliberate application of rhetorical strategies.

TRADUCEREA LITERATURII DE FICȚIUNE ÎN EPOCA DIGITALĂ: ÎN- TRE TEXT, COD ȘI INTERPRETARE /

TRANSLATING FICTION IN THE DIGITAL AGE: BETWEEN TEXT, CODE AND INTERPRETATION

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This paper explores the role of digital humanities (DH) in reshaping the theory and practice of fiction literature translation in the digital age. It starts from the premise that literary translation is no longer solely a linguistic operation but a complex, digitally mediated act that combines textual interpretation with algorithmic processing. The study examines how DH tools - such as textual corpora, stylometric analysis, visualization platforms (e.g., Voyant Tools), and neural machine translation systems (e.g., DeepL, ChatGPT) - contribute to a better understanding of literary style, narrative coherence, and cultural transfer in translated fiction. By integrating perspectives from translation studies, stylistics, and digital text analysis, the paper argues that the intersection of text, code, and interpretation fundamentally alters both how we translate and how we analyze translations. A practical case study illustrates how digital tools can assist in the comparative analysis of a source text and its translation, focusing on stylistic shifts and interpretive choices. The conclusion highlights that digitalization does not replace the literary translator but redefines their role, expanding their toolkit and encouraging new interdisciplinary approaches to fiction literature translation.

**СУЧАСНІ ПЕРЕКЛАДАЦЬКІ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ:
ТВОРИ ЛЕСІ УКРАЇНКИ ІТАЛІЙСЬКОЮ МОВОЮ
(НА МАТЕРІАЛІ ІНТЕРВ'Ю ІЗ СУЧАСНОЮ ПЕРЕКЛАДАЧКОЮ В. ДУНАС) /**

**MODERN TRANSLATIONAL TRANSFORMATIONS:
WORKS BY LESYA UKRAINKA IN ITALIAN
(BASED ON AN INTERVIEW WITH THE CONTEMPORARY
TRANSLATOR V. DUNAS)**

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The article is dedicated to the invaluable heritage of Lesya Ukrainka as a figure of Ukrainian national memory, in particular, her contributions to translation. The purpose of the article is to present the translation transformations of Lesya Ukrainka and her works. The object of the study is Italian translations of Lesya Ukrainka's works (based on an interview with the contemporary translator Vira Dunas) and scholarly sources dedicated to translations of the poetess's works. The subject of the study is the peculiarities of the translation of Lesya Ukrainka's poetic works into Polish and Italian and the translation legacy of Lesya Ukrainka in the Crimean period. Lesya Ukrainka's work and translation techniques that can be used to facilitate the transition from original units to translation units have attracted the attention of Polish (J. Lobodowski, S. Trowokhleb) and Italian (V. Dunas, L. Pompeo) scholars,

which are discussed in the article. Lesya Ukrainka's translation legacy of the Crimean period is extremely valuable. The poetess's translation activity and translations of her works are one of the ways in which Ukrainian and foreign intellectuals (people) get acquainted with the best that mankind has created in art, since it was created by the most talented representative not only of her generation in Ukrainian literature, but also among women writers in the world.

**ДО ПИТАННЯ ЗБЕРЕЖЕННЯ ОБРАЗНОЇ СИСТЕМИ АВТОРА
ПРИ ПЕРЕКЛАДІ ТВОРІВ РУМУНСЬКИХ ПОЕТІВ /**

**ON THE ISSUE OF PRESERVING THE AUTHOR'S FIGURATIVE SYSTEM
WHEN TRANSLATING WORKS OF ROMANIAN POETS**

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The research presents the author's personal experience in the field of poetic translation from Romanian into Ukrainian. In the introductory section, the 30-year experience of bilingual and multilingual education of Ukrainians at the “Alecú Russo” Balti State University is highlighted, along with the active collaboration of the university's Center for Ukrainian Language and Culture with institutions and organizations in Ukraine. This cooperation shaped the need for literary translation as one of the Center's areas of activity. The main part of the article highlights the experience of translating poetry by Moldovan and Romanian poets as part of a project by the Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Moldova aimed at translating current school textbooks into Ukrainian. As examples, translations of poems by poets Suceveanu, Vilcu, and Cosbuc intended for the textbook *Spiritual and Moral Education, Grade 2*, are presented.

**«ШКОЛА ДЛЯ ДУРАКОВ» САШИ СОКОЛОВА:
К ВОПРОСУ ОБ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ПОЭТИЧЕСКОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ РОМАНА /
SASHA SOKOLOV'S "SCHOOL FOR FOOLS": ON THE QUESTION
OF STUDYING THE POETIC STRUCTURE OF THE NOVEL**

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Intertextuality, fragmentariness, eclecticism, a combination of various styles and genres, a mixture of illusion and history, myth and modernity, a blending of different languages, cultures, truths emphasize the modernist and post-modern orientation of the novel “The School for Fools” by Sasha Sokolov. The theme of creativity and madness permeates the entire novel: the title, the image of the protagonist, the schizophrenic discourse, the associative narrative structure, and the author's position are all subordinate to the motif of creative creation.

**ПОЭТИКА РУМЫНСКОЙ НАРОДНОЙ БАЛЛАДЫ
«МАСТЕР МАНОЛЕ» В ПЕРЕВОДЕ ДАВИДА САМОЙЛОВА /
THE POETICS OF THE ROMANIAN FOLK BALLAD
“MASTER MANOLE” IN DAVID SAMOYLOV'S TRANSLATION**

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This work will focus on preserving the poetics of the Romanian folk ballad “Master Manole”, a pearl of folk art, translated by David Samoilov. The Russian poet most accurately and subtly conveyed the artistic originality of the legend, which became a source of inspiration for him. The legend was first published by the Romanian writer Vasile Alexandri under the title “Manastirea Argesului” (Monastery of Arges) in the book “Balade adunate si indreptate” (*Collected and Reworked Ballads*), Iasi, 1852. Next, Lucian Blaga showed a new interpretation of the legend, in which Manole was not punished by Negru Voda, but rather jumped off the roof. Gheorghe Voda published a collection of poems “Wings for Manole” and others. Literary ballads are a clear example of how the dialogue of cultures is developing in world literature, as well as the huge role of translations, creating a common cultural base. Translations are an important impetus for original creativity. David Samoilov (David Samuilovich Kaufman) stepped far beyond the front-line poets and constantly strived

for perfection. Time and the culture of other peoples, included in his work, significantly transformed his poetic style. New horizons opened for Samoilov, where stylization became a characteristic feature, reflecting his deep appreciation for folk art - an art form that conveys the thoughts, feelings, and experiences of the people. Folk art is defined by heightened emotionality, airiness, and musical harmony. Highly appreciating Samoilov's translations, P. Antokolsky wrote: "Samoilov has a rich vocabulary, he has an excellent command of his native language and poetry, he has sophisticated rhythmic technique and enviable intonation freedom in translating someone else's colloquial speech". The Romanian ballad, translated by Samoilov, acquired an independent life in its native poetic and linguistic element. He used the techniques of transformation, metamorphosis, Romanian rhythm, motives, images, which allowed him to create a picture of life as constant movement and the transformation of artistic forms into each other. He used comparison techniques - "Anna-beauty", "flower of the field"; metaphors - "dressing a wife, dressing her in stone", "she was bent by the wind", "the building grew up", "the wall is shaking me, squeezing my ribs, breaking my child!"; epithets - "for good memory", "Beauty Anna", "the first craftsman", "lesser craftsmen", "great architects", in which he drew the reader's attention to important details, ancient myths of the Romanesque peoples, telling about the founding of cities, castles, towers, etc. Samoilov succeeded in characteristic mythological thinking and the motive of merging the natural world with the human. In this ballad, Samoilov embodied in detail the mechanism of "creative" death, which has passed down from ancient beliefs to our time, as well as the image of a hero who freely and confidently feels himself an organic part of the world.

**ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ИКОНИЧЕСКОЙ ПАРЕМИИ
В ОРИГИНАЛЬНОМ И ПЕРЕВОДНОМ ТЕКСТАХ
(НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ДИСКУРСА В. ШУКШИНА) /**

**THE FUNCTIONING OF ICONIC PAREMIOLOGY
IN ORIGINAL AND TRANSLATED TEXTS
(BASED ON THE LITERARY DISCOURSE OF V. SHUKSHIN)**

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The research focuses on the functioning of iconic paroemia in the original and translated texts (on the basis of V. Shukshin’s fictional discourse). V. Shukshin’s creative activity has become the scope of the study of both Russian and a lot of foreign researchers as in the writer’s literary works the author’s and characters’ voices are uniquely individual. In certain instances occasional paroemia is used in the author’s fictional discourse, which is certain to impede the correlation of such phrases into the Romanian language within the limits of the equivalency of the common linguistic units of the Russian and Romanian phraseological stock. Upon analyzing phraseologisms, we conclude that their equivalents are exact on the semantic level and less frequently precise on the lexical one, which proves the crucial significance of iconic paroemia not only within the language system, but also within fictional discourse.

**CURRENT APPROACHES
TO TERMINOLOGY TRANSLATION AND INTERPRETING**

GLOBALIZATION AND ITS IMPACT ON TRANSLATION COMPETENCE: A TRANSLATION STUDIES PERSPECTIVE

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The phenomenon of globalization has profoundly reshaped the landscape of translation, demanding new competencies from translators operating in an increasingly interconnected world. This article explores the multifaceted impact of globalization on translation competence from a translation studies perspective. It examines how global communication flows, the dominance of English as a *lingua franca*, and the rise of digital technologies have transformed the skills, knowledge, and strategies required of professional translators. Drawing on theoretical frameworks and recent research, the study identifies key components of translation competence in the global context, including intercultural awareness, technological proficiency, and adaptability to diverse textual and cultural environments. The article argues that translation is no longer a purely linguistic activity but a dynamic, interdisciplinary practice influenced by socio-economic and cultural globalization. The findings underscore the need for updated translator training models that reflect the complex demands of globalized communication.

CROSS-LINGUISTIC CHALLENGES IN TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Phraseological units – such as idioms, collocations, set similes and multi-word expressions – pose significant challenges in translation and interpreting due to their culturally bound meanings and structural specificity. This presentation explores the cross-linguistic difficulties involved in rendering such expressions across Russian, Romanian, English, and German. By analyzing idiomatic structures and strategies for equivalence, the study highlights how cultural context, syntactic flexibility, and metaphorical meaning influence translation choices. The research draws on examples from literary, journalistic, and spoken discourse, aiming to identify patterns, pitfalls, and effective solutions for maintaining both meaning and stylistic nuance in multilingual contexts.

CHALLENGES OF IT TERMINOLOGY TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH INTO ROMANIAN BASED ON THE CLARIN PARALLEL CORPUS

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The growing internationalization of IT underscores the urgent need for accurate and consistent translation of IT terminology from English into Romanian. This study focuses especially on data from the Romanian–English parallel corpus developed within the CLARIN infrastructure. The research categorizes translation techniques into direct and indirect methods and assesses their frequency and effectiveness based on corpus data. A subcorpus of 5,000 aligned IT term pairs was compiled and analyzed to determine the distribution of methods such as calque, borrowing, transposition, modulation, and equivalence. The results show that calque (42%) and borrowing (25%) are the most common methods for transferring IT terminology into Romanian, while transposition (8%), modulation (5%), and equivalence (3–4%) ensure idiomatic accuracy and functional clarity. The study demonstrates how bilingual corpora, particularly those from CLARIN, can support empirical research in technical translation.

NATIONAL VARIATIONS IN LEGAL TERMINOLOGY. THE BRITISH AND AMERICAN PERSPECTIVE

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The aim of the research is to investigate the cultural specificity underlying the composition of British and American legal terminologies. Despite a common origin in the Anglo-Saxon and Roman legal traditions, British Legal Terminology (BLT) and American Legal Terminology (ALT) have undergone particular developments due to various socio-political, historical, and cultural conditions. The study analyzes distinctions in taxonomic structures, paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations, and the use of proprial terms. Special attention is given to the role of internationalisms and terminological synonymy, revealing how extralinguistic factors influence the evolution and structure of legal language. The findings underscore the dynamic interplay between linguistic universality and national legal identity.

**TRADUIRE LE LEXIQUE CHRÉTIEN-ORTHODOXE.
QUELQUES ÉQUIVALENCES RITUELLES, LITURGIQUES ET SPIRITUELLES /
TRANSLATING THE CHRISTIAN-ORTHODOX LEXICON.
SOME RITUAL, LITURGICAL AND SPIRITUAL EQUIVALENTS**

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We propose a translational analysis of some ritual, liturgical and spiritual equivalents for certain Romanian and French words, encountered in texts of Orthodox theology and spirituality submitted for translation between the two Romance languages. We are working on a corpus of specialized translations of such texts, between Romanian and French, in both directions of the translational act, which we have carried out ourselves from a number of theologian authors who are consecrated in both cultures. Given the socio-religious particularities of these two cultures, Romanian and French, the confessional equivalences proposed for words with Orthodox specificities are subject to critical evaluation of the prescriptive norms of the linguistic imaginary constructed by the readers of these versions, coupled with a cultural imaginary. We will analyze several equivalences that must be used to “properly” translate the Orthodox-Christian lexicon, which we have classified as ritual, liturgical and spiritual.

**QUELQUES PRINCIPES DE FONCTIONNEMENT
DES BASES TERMINOLOGIQUES ET DES MÉMOIRES DE TRADUCTION /
SOME OPERATING PRINCIPLES OF TERMINOLOGY BASES
AND TRANSLATION MEMORIES**

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Our research aims to explain some of the operating principles of certain essential tools for translators: terminology databases and translation memories. While terminology databases provide valuable support for ensuring the consistency and accuracy of translations, translation memories are more focused on reducing translation costs and better managing the time allocated to the translation process. We will highlight the role of these two tools in accelerating and standardizing the translator's work, while integrating other tools involved in computer-assisted translation. Automation and structured storage of linguistic data can help organize and systematize information content in a more technical manner to enable faster information sharing.

**EMPLOI DU PASSÉ COMPOSÉ
PAR LES APPRENANTS DU SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL AU GHANA /
USE OF THE PASSÉ COMPOSÉ
BY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN GHANA**

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This article focuses on the difficulties encountered by Senior High School students in Ghana in using the present perfect tense (*passé composé*) in French. Our objective is to determine how students apply the radical, inflexion, auxiliaries and past participle of this tense in their oral and written communications. A particular attention is given to its semantic aspects, especially how the *passé composé* conveys meanings related to pure actions, processes, continuity, subject and attribute, existence of the subject, and transitions from one state to another.

**LES CONTRAINTES DU PROCESSUS DE LA TRADUCTION
DU LANGAGE DIPLOMATIQUE ET POLITIQUE :
IMPLICATIONS DANS LA TRANSPOSITION DIDACTIQUE /
THE CONSTRAINTS OF THE TRANSLATION PROCESS
OF DIPLOMATIC AND POLITICAL LANGUAGE:
IMPLICATIONS FOR DIDACTIC TRANSPOSITION**

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This article explores the unique challenges encountered when translating diplomatic and political language, highlighting its implications for didactic transposition, meaning the application of these translations within an educational context. An analysis emphasizes the specificities of diplomatic and political language, which is characterized by often complex vocabulary, figurative expressions, subtle nuances, and specific cultural connotations, requiring a particular translation approach. Lastly, an aspect underlining the importance of a nuanced and well-informed approach to translating diplomatic and political language is discussed. Translators must be aware of cultural implications and diplomatic subtleties while maintaining the integrity of the messages when transposing these texts into the educational and pedagogical framework. Teaching translation in these fields must take these challenges into account and help learners develop the specific skills necessary to succeed in this highly specialized area.

**PROBLÈME LEXICOLOGIQUE ET DE SÉMANTIQUE :
DIFFICULTÉS DE TRANSPOSITION DE LA TRADUCTION
ET DE L'INTERPRÉTATION DU LEXIQUE ÉWÉ
EN LANGUES ÉTRANGÈRES POUR LA TRANSMISSION
DES RÉSULTATS DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE /
LEXICOLOGICAL AND SEMANTIC ISSUES:
DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATING AND INTERPRETING
THE EWE LEXICON INTO FOREIGN LANGUAGES
FOR THE TRANSMISSION OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH FINDINGS**

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Our study focuses on the translation and interpretation of items from the Ewe language, a language of Togo, from the Niger-Congo family and the Kwa sub-branch. This study aims to demonstrate the difficulties that the researcher has in translating and interpreting research results in the major languages used for scientific dissemination, with the goal of reaching a wider audience and gaining recognition for the research undertaken. In the particular case of Togolese linguists, the trend favours publications in two languages with weight on the international scene, if it concerns scientific dissemination. These languages are English and French. However, it turns out that the translation and interpretation of Ewe in these languages, especially in French,

the language on which we will base ourselves more, is very difficult and complicated. To carry out this research, we propose to conduct it with the theory of 20th century structuralism, and especially on Ducrot's (1968) thesis, which stipulates that structure is based on the language system and represents any regular organization of linguistic structures. Ducrot further clarifies that once linguistic structures become objects of study, the issue addressed by this research is linked to the application of the principle of independence between structure and semantics. This highlights the difficulties involved in transmitting an identical semantic idea through structurally different sentences.

**CERTAINES CONSIDÉRATIONS SUR LES PARTICULARITÉS
PSYCHOLINGUISTIQUES DE LA TRADUCTION ET DE L'AUTOTRADUC-
TION COMME PROCESSUS DE MÉDIATION CULTURELLE /
SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC PECULIARITIES
OF TRANSLATION AND SELF-TRANSLATION AS A PROCESS
OF CULTURAL MEDIATION**

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In this research we try to examine the psycholinguistic peculiarities of translation and self-translation as a process of cultural mediation in multilingual spaces. It adopts a multidisciplinary approach (primarily psycholinguistic, but also experimental, comparative, and analytical at the discourse level), focusing on the Republic of Moldova, where several languages coexist, including Romanian, Russian, Gagauz, and Ukrainian, among others. The data from the Republic of Moldova are compared with those recorded in other multilingual societies (such as Canada, Belgium, Switzerland, and Catalonia). Validated data (censuses, empirical studies) are used to support the analysis. The investigation is theoretically grounded in the works of Grosjean, Jeanneret, Pavlenko, Kroll, Bialystok, and others. Two tables that summarize the demolinguistic data and the comparative and cognitive performances support the research. This leads

to the proposal of a model that schematizes linguistic distribution in the Republic of Moldova, alongside another that illustrates in detail the cerebral mechanisms of bilingualism in general, and Bessarabian bilingualism in particular. Concrete cases (bilingual writers, educational policies) are also mentioned and presented to argue the theoretical approach. The analysis demonstrates that translation and self-translation involve cognitive mechanisms of inhibition and control specific to bilinguals, shaping complex identity dynamics. These linguistic processes are strongly influenced by the sociocultural context, including language status, linguistic policies, and inter-ethnic contacts. In conclusion, we emphasize the importance of considering psycholinguistic dimensions in language education, cultural mediation, the understanding of identity dynamics in bilingual communities, and the processes of translation and self-translation.

**ABKÜRZUNGEN IN WISSENSCHAFTLICHEN TEXTEN:
HERAUSFORDERUNGEN DER ÜBERSETZUNG
ZWISCHEN FACH- UND ALLTAGSSPRACHE /**

**ABBREVIATIONS IN ACADEMIC TEXTS: CHALLENGES
OF TRANSLATION BETWEEN SPECIALIZED AND EVERYDAY LANGUAGE**

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This research explores the use and translation of abbreviations in specialized and everyday language, focusing on German and Romanian. It discusses linguistic economy, context sensitivity, and stylistic and cultural variation. Special emphasis is placed on academic communication and the interlingual transfer of abbreviations. The study highlights the need for standardization through abbreviation lists to avoid misinterpretation. By analyzing common patterns and differences, the article aims to provide practical guidelines for the consistent and norm-compliant use of abbreviations in scholarly texts, promoting clarity, terminological precision, and mutual understanding across languages and academic disciplines.

**TRADUZIONE ED ESPRESSIONI POLIREMATICHE.
UNO STUDIO CONTRASTIVO ITALIANO-ROMENO /
TRANSLATION AND POLYREMIC EXPRESSIONS.
A CONTRASTIVE STUDY BETWEEN ITALIAN AND ROMANIAN**

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In the formation of the loan translations, the correct equivalence of the polyrematic expressions from the source language to the target language is very important and it can be supported by the parallelism between the two languages. But in the case of closely related languages, there is a clear distinction between the loan translation and the parallelism or the equivalence, and this can lead to a confusion between the two linguistic phenomena. Our analysis of the interferences between two Romance languages, Italian and Romanian, allowed us to make an inventory of a number of polyrematic expressions referring to the parts of the human body. Among all types of loan translation, the phraseological one seems to be clearly the most common.

**PROCEDEE DE TRADUCERE A NUMELOR PROPRII
DIN DICȚIONARUL LUI ANDREAS CLEMENS /
TRANSLATION TECHNIQUES OF PROPER NOUNS
IN ANDREAS CLEMENS' DICTIONARY**

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In Andreas Clemens' bilingual dictionary (Buda, 1821) there are numerous proper nouns of different categories – anthroponyms, toponyms, theonyms, etc., in German and Romanian, giving the dictionary a distinctly didactic character. These nouns are culturally charged and indirectly provide information about the ethnic German community for which the dictionary is intended as a tool for learning Romanian. The Romanian equivalent is usually used to translate the German name, and this practice is carried out through various methods, such as word-for-word translation, explanatory translation, total equivalence or adapting the name into the Romanian language system. In this research, we aim to inventory and explain the translation methods that the author used to render the Romanian equivalents of proper nouns in the German part of the dictionary.

**IMPACTUL TRADUCERILOR TEHNICE
ASUPRA EXPERIENȚEI UTILIZATORULUI:
CAZUL LOCALIZĂRII MICROSOFT OFFICE ÎN LIMBA ROMÂNĂ /**

**THE IMPACT OF TECHNICAL TRANSLATIONS ON USER EXPERIENCE:
THE CASE OF MICROSOFT OFFICE LOCALIZATION INTO ROMANIAN**

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In the current context of accelerated digitalization, software localization is no longer a matter of linguistic transfer alone, but a complex process of cultural and functional adaptation with direct implications for user experience (UX). This article examines the influence of technical translations on how Romanian-speaking users interact with the Romanian-language interface of Microsoft Office LTSC Professional Plus 2024. The primary objective is to identify problematic linguistic formulations – ambiguous,

overly literal, or contextually inadequate – and to assess their effects on the clarity, efficiency, and predictability of user interaction. The study adopts a mixed-method approach, combining a comparative analysis of terminology between the Romanian and English versions of the software with an observational investigation conducted within the academic course "Information and Communication Technologies". Qualitative data, collected from feedback provided by students in non-IT fields, enabled a direct correlation between localization deficiencies and practical usability challenges. The results indicate that inadequate translations can compromise both the functionality and accessibility of software, particularly for users with limited digital literacy. The conclusions underscore the need for rigorous localization processes supported by collaboration between linguists, technical translators, software developers, and UX professionals. The article offers a set of recommendations aimed at improving software localization, emphasizing terminological consistency, linguistic clarity, and cultural appropriateness.

**PROVOCĂRILE TERMINOLOGIEI ȘI TRANSFERULUI CONCEPTUAL
ÎN DISCURSUL REGELUI FILIP AL VI-LEA AL SPANIEI:
O PERSPECTIVĂ PRAGMATICĂ /**

**THE CHALLENGES OF TERMINOLOGY AND CONCEPTUAL TRANSFER
IN THE DISCOURSE OF KING FELIPE VI OF SPAIN:
A PRAGMATIC PERSPECTIVE**

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This presentation explores the challenges of terminology and conceptual transfer in the discourse of King Felipe VI, focusing on diplomatic ceremonial contexts. From a pragmatic perspective, royal discourse is shaped by culturally embedded values, institutional roles and historical community. Translating or analyzing such discourse involves navigating terms with no direct equivalents and concepts tied to national identity, tradition, or constitutional monarchy. We examine how politeness, strategies, deixis and implicit meaning require careful interpretation. These elements pose challenges not only for translation, but also for ensuring the speakers intended image and authority are accurately conveyed across languages and cultures.

**SEMNIFICAȚIILE TERMENULUI „INFRAȚIUNE” ÎN ROMÂNĂ
ȘI RUSĂ, ȘI IMPACTUL LOR ASUPRA SISTEMELOR JURIDIC
ȘI SOCIAL ALE REPUBLICII MOLDOVA /**

**THE MEANINGS OF THE TERM "INFRAȚIUNE" IN ROMANIAN
AND RUSSIAN, AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE LEGAL
AND SOCIAL SYSTEMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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This research explores the terminological meaning of the Romanian word "infrațiuune" through a multi-faceted analysis, including linguistic, legal and socio-logical perspectives. The study highlights the historical evolution of the term, its use in different fields and the impact on the legal system and society. The legal interpretation of the term "infrațiuune " in the legal norms of the Republic of Moldova and the impact of translation on applicability and perception.

**ЛІНГВІСТИЧНІ СТРАТЕГІЇ РОСІЙСЬКО-УКРАЇНСЬКОЇ ВІЙНИ:
РОЛЬ ПЕРЕКЛАДУ У ФОРМУВАННІ ЦІННІСНИХ ОРІЄНТИРІВ /**
**LINGUISTIC STRATEGIES OF THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR:
THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN SHAPING VALUE ORIENTATIONS**

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The Russian-Ukrainian war has become an all-encompassing event in our lives. It affects not only every man and woman in Ukraine, but also all spheres of our lives, everything we live by and everything we live in. A distinctive feature of the current war is that it is being fought on all fronts and at all levels: from the physical to the virtual and informational, where every word and every symbol has meaning. Language in war is a powerful weapon and an equally powerful tool of manipulation. At the same time, it is a manifestation of 'soft power,' which is used to exert a systematic influence on the population's consciousness and subconscious. Therefore, analysing the impact of linguistic strategies on the formation of citizens' value orientations is necessary not only in theory but, above all, in practice. Since the start of Russian aggression against Ukraine, new words and terms have entered our everyday vocabulary, the translation of which is crucial for understanding both the situation and the enemy's intentions, not to mention the fact that manipulative

translation leads to distortion of meaning and the formation of attitudes distorted by enemy propaganda, which ultimately hurts the stability and unity of the nation. Among the neologisms of modern warfare. For example, at the beginning of the large-scale war, the term ‘makronity’ entered the Ukrainian language, meaning ‘to look concerned about a certain situation, but not to take effective steps to resolve it.’ This neologism originates from the surname of E. Macron, the French president, who in 2022 frequently expressed concern, which in turn did not go unnoticed by Ukrainians. Translation plays a crucial role in information warfare, as the same events can be conveyed differently to the audience through ‘wordplay.’ This problem is particularly acute on social media, where a significant portion of society obtains most of its news and analytical information. The research also draws attention to language strategies for protecting national identity, tested by modern warfare, as well as translation as a form of counter-propaganda. The author focuses on linguistic techniques, specifically the use of language forms and their impact on the perception of events unfolding on the fronts of the information war.

**З ПЕРЕКЛАДАЦЬКОГО ДОСВІДУ ІНТЕГРУВАННЯ УКРАЇНЦІВУ
ПОЛІКУЛЬТУРНЕ СЕРЕДОВИЩЕ РЕСПУБЛІКИ МОЛДОВА /
FROM THE TRANSLATION EXPERIENCE OF INTEGRATING
UKRAINIANS INTO THE MULTICULTURAL ENVIRONMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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In the work of the Ukrainian Language and Culture Center of “Alecu Russo” Balti State University translation activities are of particular importance. However, the Center's main goal is scientific, didactic, cultural and educational orientation aimed at preserving, researching and promoting the Ukrainian language and culture of Ukrainians in Moldova, as well as fostering ties with Ukrainians in Ukraine within the particular conditions of living in the multilingual environment of Moldova, where Romanian and Ukrainian are among the primary functioning languages. In the process of comprehending cultural, literary, linguistic phenomena and historical events in the destinies of our peoples, translation activity plays a guiding role in creating an intellectual identity and forming public opinion. The Ukrainian translation of literary works of contemporary Bessarabian postmodernist poets, carried out by our authors in 2012, has strengthened the current Ukrainian-Romanian literary ties, revealing common guidelines and the development of both literatures. The Ukrainian-Romanian

translation has acquired particular resonance and significance in recent years, marked by tragic events in Ukraine. Romanian and Bessarabian poets and writers, journalists and publishers were among the first to actively respond, expressing a strong desire to be heard by Ukrainians in their messages of solidarity and support for the Ukrainian people in their struggle for independence. One of the first areas of focus was to meet the social communication needs of Ukrainian citizens, who were forced to leave their homes and seek refuge in Moldova. This led to the essential production of translated educational and didactic materials for children, textbooks for pupils, and phrasebooks for adults who had settled in Romanian-language environments. This activity has also become crucial for the Ukrainian population of Moldova, as the second-largest ethnic group in the country after the titular one, in providing opportunities to study in their native language. Intellectual communication was also supported by Bessarabian poets, who were among the first to respond to the tragic events in Ukraine. Their poetry not only concentrates human emotions, but also reflects on the processes that caused the disasters, their consequences, and the numerous human, cultural, spiritual, and material losses. This resulted in the emergence of Romanian poetry, translated by us into Ukrainian. Some of these texts were published in literary magazines in Moldova and Romania. A bilingual poetry edition is currently being prepared for publication. Cooperation with leading Moldovan online publications has also proven significant. For example, the Moldovan branch of the Romanian media outlet *Timpul* published our Romanian-language translation of an interview with the late Ukrainian poet Maksym Kryvtsov, along with translations of his poetry. Subsequent editions featured Romanian translations of texts by Andriy Lyubka and Oksana Shchur. A meaningful and encouraging translation experience is reflected in the Romanian-Ukrainian two-volume edition, a 15-year-long project exploring family roots and chronicling the history of a family united by both Ukrainian and Romanian heritage. Thus, the article presents the role and main results of the translation activities carried out by scholars of the Ukrainian Language and Culture Center of “Alecu Russo” Balti State University, which reflect the stages of life of our society in the XXIst century.

**ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ТРАНСЛІТЕРАЦІЇ ВЛАСНИХ ІМЕН
(З ДОСВІДУ ПЕРЕКЛАДУ ДОКУМЕНТІВ) /
PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLITERATION OF PROPER NOUNS
(FROM THE EXPERIENCE OF TRANSLATING DOCUMENTS)**

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In the current context of globalization, as well as intensive labor and educational migration, the transliteration of proper nouns in translated documents is becoming increasingly significant. The correct rendering of names and surnames directly affects such critically important aspects as the legal accuracy of documents, the ability to unambiguously identify individuals in different countries, compliance with international and national standards, and the prevention of legal, bureaucratic, or everyday difficulties. This issue is particularly relevant for Ukrainian citizens who obtain residence permits or temporary protection abroad (especially in Moldova and Romania), study, work, or conclude contracts in other countries, apply for dual citizenship, submit documents for diploma recognition, inheritance procedures, and more. In translation practice, this leads to a major challenge: the absence of a unified national system for the transliteration of Ukrainian names into Romanian in the Republic of Moldova. In contrast, Ukraine has had an official transliteration system since 2010 (Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 55), used for issuing passports, with verification available

on the State Migration Service website. On the international level, the following standards are relevant: ISO 9:1997 — Cyrillic-to-Latin transliteration with diacritics, and SR 13456:2000 — a simplified version without diacritics. This study is based on the translator's practical experience working with personal documents (passports, certificates, diplomas, powers of attorney, etc.) between 2007 and 2025. It analyzes common issues in rendering iotated vowels, soft consonants, the letter “r”, sibilants, affricates, and cases where names are written without modification. Comparisons are made between the Ukrainian passport-based transliteration system (CMU 2010) and forms adapted to Romanian orthography. To address this issue in translation practice, two main approaches are used: (1) preserving the Latinized form of names and surnames as shown in the Ukrainian international passport — a legitimate and official method, especially for notarial, legal, or immigration-related translations; and (2) adapting to Romanian linguistic norms — suitable for informal, educational, and less formalized contexts, with attention to phonetics and orthography. The conclusion emphasizes that proper name transliteration is not only a technical but also a legal matter, requiring accuracy, responsibility, and knowledge of regulatory frameworks in both Ukraine and the target country. The lack of a unified Romanian transliteration system demands professional flexibility and careful case-by-case analysis from translators. The best practice remains to use the official Ukrainian document spelling, which has legal force in most situations. The research also provides general recommendations for translators: always check name spelling against the Ukrainian international passport; in case of discrepancies, consult the client, embassy, or relevant official authority; and avoid altering legitimate spellings, even if they appear unusual in Romanian. When translating for use in Romania or Moldova, be sure to consider local legal practices and translation requirements. Therefore, the chosen topic is strategic for translation professionals, particularly those working in notarial, immigration, legal, and educational domains. Accurate transliteration is not just about “correct spelling” - it is the key to legal recognition of a person, their documents, and their rights abroad.

**ЛИНГВОКОГНИТИВНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЕРБАЛИЗАЦИИ
КОНЦЕПТА «СТРАХ» В ЯЗЫКОВЫХ КАРТИНАХ РУССКОГО
И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЭТНОСА /**

**LINGUOCOGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF THE VERBALIZATION
OF THE CONCEPT OF "FEAR" IN THE LINGUISTIC REPRESENTATIONS
OF THE RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH ETHNOS**

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The process of changing the linguistic paradigm has led to the objectification of mental phenomena using the notion of “concept”, which has its own specifics in cognitive science and linguocultural studies. This is one aspect of the relevance of the study, the second is related to the need to correct this concept and clarify the means of its representation. The aim of the work is to analyze the objectification of the concept of “fear” in the linguistic worldviews of the Russian and English ethnicities. The work methodology is based on the conceptual principles of the aforementioned sciences. In the analysis of linguistic facts, various methods were used, including: same analysis, the method of dictionary definitions, etymological analysis, and field structuring. Results of the study: a definition of the concept of “fear” in Russian and English is given; based on the proposed definition, the concept is structured, and the core and periphery of the concept are identified. Comparing the specifics of the concept in two languages, we come to the conclusion that in both languages it is possible to identify both integral and differential semantic features of the specified concept.

**СПЕЦИФИКА БЕЗЭКВИВАЛЕНТНОСТИ
В ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ РУССКОГО И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ /
THE SPECIFICS OF NON-EQUIVALENCE IN THE LEXICAL SYSTEM
OF RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES**

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The relevance of the study lies in the growing interest in exploring foreign-language cultures, driven by the strengthening of international contacts. The aim of the research is to identify the most effective strategies for translating non-equivalent vocabulary between English and Russian. The concepts of "non-equivalent vocabulary", "realia", "lacuna" are defined; the methods of conveying the semantics of non-equivalent vocabulary in translation are described. The types of interlingual lexical non-equivalence are analyzed. The paper concludes that explication is the most effective method of conveying the semantics of non-equivalent vocabulary into English.

**CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH
IN MASS-MEDIA TRANSLATION AND INTERPRETATION**

**CONTRIBUTION DE L'INTELLIGENCE ARTIFICIELLE (IA)
DANS L'ÉVOLUTION DE LA TRADUCTION MODERNE /
CONTRIBUTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)
TO THE EVOLUTION OF MODERN TRANSLATION**

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Artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized translation through neural models (such as DeepL and GPT-4), offering speed and accessibility for standardized texts. However, its limitations persist: difficulties in capturing cultural nuances, creativity (literature, humor), and risks of critical errors (legal, medical). AI complements rather than replaces human translators, who remain essential for post-editing and contextual adaptation. Hybrid tools (cloud-based translation memories, CAT tools) optimize efficiency, while automation reduces costs. Yet, ethical challenges (data biases, confidentiality) and technical limitations (lack of coherence, specialized vocabulary) highlight the need for human-machine collaboration. Modern translators must master these technologies and specialize in complex domains where AI falls short. In the future, AI could integrate encyclopedic knowledge to improve nuance and enable real-time translation. However, its success will depend on rigorous ethical frameworks and synergy with human expertise, combining technological productivity with cultural sensitivity. The translation of tomorrow will thus be hybrid, combining the power of AI with the finesse of professionals.

**LA TRADUCTION DES BANDES-ANNONCES
COMME ACTE DE DISCOURS MULTIMODAL /
TRANSLATING FILM TRAILERS
AS AN ACT OF MULTIMODAL DISCOURSE**

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The movie trailer presents a specific form of audiovisual discourse with a persuasive function, built on a fragmentary and symbolic narrative structure. Beyond its informational and movie promotion dimension, it functions as a multimodal product composed of semiotic elements and verbal text that interact and complement each other. The translation of the trailer therefore becomes an act of discursive and cultural (re)construction. This paper proposes an exploration of trailer translation from an intersemiotic perspective, analyzing how audiovisual translation negotiates meaning in a condensed and dynamic communicative framework, drawing attention to how localization strategies succeed (or not) in balancing technical constraints, cultural requirements and target audience expectations.